

DEVELOPMENT OF BEND-FORMING TECHNOLOGIES ON CF RTP TUBE

Tatsuya Banno¹, Armin Rashidi², Bryn Crawford², Abbas S Milani², Asami Nakai³

¹ Gifu University, Graduate school of natural science and technology, Gifu, Gifu, Japan

² Composite Research Network-Okanagan Laboratory, School of Engineering,
University of British Columbia, Kelowna, BC, Canada.

³ Gifu University, Faculty of Engineering, Gifu, Gifu, Japan.

Keywords: Forming, Thermal forming, Braided composite, Thermoplastic composite

ABSTRACT

As the demand of textile composites is incredibly increasing in recent years, the understanding of forming behaviour, defects on textile composites still needs improvement to make the most use of its light weight and strong structure. Currently, many researches on composite forming have been done in many countries to realize complex shaped items made by textile composite materials [1,2]. One of the representative complex shaped items are bend-formed tube used for many automobile parts. To apply bend-formed technologies into composite braided tube, the mechanism of bend-deformation needs to be clarified. In this research, the simple approach for thermal bend-forming simulation on braided CF RTP tubes were implemented using general material characterization method and simulation techniques. Firstly, the tensile responses were compared with the thermal tensile experiment which have been done in the past to evaluate the deformation performance under unidirectional tensile condition. The bend-forming motion was then challenged to predict defects, limits reliability of forming.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, forming technologies for composite materials have been rapidly developed from many research groups all around the world. Prepreg compression forming (PCF) process is well known to have the highest productivity among other manufacturing processes for CF RTP products. Although on these kinds of flat forming process, there are geometrical limit to create complex shapes. Especially to produce complex shaped items with cylindrical geometrics, techniques and knowledge needs to be developed. Also, simulation techniques to predict defects during the process has been actively developed by many researchers. In this research, both experiment and numerical approach has been challenged to investigate the bend-forming mechanism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

Bend-forming technique selected in this research is a classic method used for metal tube bending (Fig.1). By using this old but simple forming method, not only to reduce production cost but to improve degree of freedom for design can both be realized at the same time. Curvature radius can be chosen by several kinds of bending die made in different curvature radius. In this research R300 curvature radius bending die has been chosen for forming. The straight CF RTP tube with inner core inside was placed on the bending machine shown at Fig.1. The heating device is attached to the machine to heat up the tube before forming. Bend-forming deformation is composed of bending motion and tensioning. Tensioning will be preventing wrinkling at the inner circumference side of bending section. Displacement will be added longitudinally to tension the pipe and it can be controlled by plotting the coordinates on left chuck device movement. All these commands can be processed automatically by bending machine only with few inputs of basic information through control panel. After bend-forming process, it only needs to be cooled down naturally by air. The tube after finishing all the process is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1 Bend-forming method.

Fig.2 Bend-formed CFRTP tube after forming.

2.1 CFRTP TUBES FOR BEND-FORMING

Two different kinds of CFRTP tubes, braiding and Filament winding (FW) were prepared for bend-forming (Fig.3). Each tube was made in different processing condition and method shown in Table 1 to unify both thickness and outer diameter close to 1.5mm and 30mm, respectively. Carbon fiber used for these tubes are produced from both Toray and Mitsubishi Chemical. While, resin material was produced from Mitsubishi Gas Chemical Corporation. This resin material has melting and glass transition point at 213°C and 63°C respectively. Both carbon and resin yarn materials were mingled and pre-impregnated beforehand. This Partially impregnated Commingled Yarn (PCY) was used for making both FW and braiding CFRTP tubes by reheating the yarns over melting temperature. Also from the experiment done in the past, deflection temperature underload for the tube has been detected as 190°C. This temperature is where the tube starts deforming and as it is below melting point, forming process can be done without melting completely.

Fig.3 CFRTP tube structures.

Table.1: Materials and condition.

	Materials		Conditions	
	CF	Resin	Ply	wind/braid condition
Braiding	T800SC-24000	LEXTER8500	5	45° 16yarns
FW	TR50S_6L	LEXTER8500	6	45° helical wind

2.2 BEND-FORMABILITY OF CFRTP TUBES

Carbon fiber cannot be stretched as it only has elongation for less than 10%. In order to deform textile composite structures, fiber orientation needs to be changed during forming process. Textile composite forming motion combines both compression and tensile deformation during the process. At the outer circumferential side of bending section, fibers become stretched while on the inner side it becomes compressed. Compressed area made topical can easily make wrinkling at the surface. Way to prevent wrinkling at the inner side is where it needs knowledge and techniques as it can become fundamental factor of fracturing the item.

To figure out the best structure for tube forming, FW and braiding tubes were compared for their flexibility. From the bend-forming experiment, both tubes achieved the target radius of R300 and showed great formability (Fig.4). As R300 bend-forming could not show limits of flexibility enough, uni-directional tensile experiment was implemented. From the results, FW had better stretching than braiding as it displaced bigger amount. Although braiding showed less displacement, diameter became thin than FW tube (Fig.5). This describes that braiding is better to use for smaller curvature radius forming. As FW deforms by moving the entire section, braiding is better to make small curvature locally.

6K-FW pipe

6K-braided pipe

Fig.4 FW and braiding tubes after forming.

Fig.5 Uni-directional tensile test.

3 SIMULATION AND COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH

To reduce experimental cost, computational method has been implemented in many forming researches these days. In this research simple macro scale modeling and simulation using non-linear Finite Element code LS-DYNA was challenged to predict limits and search for details of bend-forming mechanism. In LS-DYNA, there are several ways to model reinforced thermoplastic composite materials in shell element. As for forming simulation, MAT_REINFORCED_THERMOPLASTIC (249) is introduced to describe shear deformation between the fibers which can calculate up to three fiber family direction [3]. By PART_COMPOSITE keyword command, the material can be laminated using different integration point through thickness. Other model is combination of fabric model and thermoplastic model. For woven fabric models MAT_VISCOELASTIC_LOOSE_FABRIC (234) and MAT_MICROMECHANICS_DRY_FABRIC (235) can be used. The forming simulation method using these fabric models have been introduced by Ala Tabiei [4]. Although, never been used for cylindrical item model nor tube bend-forming simulation. In this research, several type of model for bend forming was compared for their formability and performance reliability. Firstly, simple tensile forming simulation was challenged using material models. To make it simple as possible, braiding tube was created only by shell element. Dominant deformation modes for braided tubes are similar to general woven fabric forming. The major deformation is in-plane shear between fiber family and out-of-plane bending behavior. The most famous material characterization method to extract shear behavior is bias-extension test (Fig.6). Other major inputs like Uni-direction tensile properties were detected from 0/90° Uni-axial tensile test. From these basic properties tensile forming simulation model was created shown in Fig.7. From the simulation results in Fig.8, the load-displacement curves showed much higher values than experimental data. The stiffness of shell element might be affecting the load curves. From other simulation implemented by membrane element the load curves showed lower values and became close to experimental results. To improve simulation accuracy, shell-membrane element model needs to be tried to describe the real stiffness of braiding tubes as much as possible.

Fig.6 Bias-extension test for braiding.

Fig.7 Tensile simulation on braiding CFRTTP forming shell model (MAT249).

Fig.8 Results on Load and Orientation angle from tensile simulation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

From bend-forming and uni-directional tensile experiment, braiding showed a tendency better to create small curvature radius locally on bend-formed item. Bend-forming simulation challenged by shell element could not describe tensile responses correctly as shell element makes the model too stiff for deformation. To improve accuracy, elements combined with shell and membrane needs to be challenged.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is supported from many companies and academic associations. Author Especially thanks to the support for simulation and material characterization from JSOL corporation and UBC CRN Okanagan team.

REFERENCES

- [1] Masato Nishi, Tei Hirashima, Sean Wang, "Constitutive Modeling for Composite Forming Simulation and Development of a Tool for Composite Material Design". 14th International LS-DYNA Users.
- [2] G. Hivet, P. Boisse, "Consistent mesoscopic mechanical behavior model for woven composite reinforcements in biaxial tension", *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Vol.39, pp.345-361, (2008).
- [3] M. Grubenmann, J. Heingartner, P. Hora, D. Bassan, "Influence of temperature on in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical behavior of GFRP composite". *IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 1063(2018).
- [4] Ala Tabiei, Raguram Murugesan, "Thermal Structural Forming Simulation of Carbon and Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics Composites". *International Journal of Composite Materials* 2015, 5(69: 182-194).